

Oxidative C-H Homocoupling of Push-Pull Benzothiazoles: An Atom-Economical Route to Highly Emissive Quadrupolar Arylamine-Functionalized 2,2'-Bibenzothiazoles with Enhanced Two-Photon Absorption

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Supporting Information Placeholder

ABSTRACT: Copper(II)-catalyzed C-H/C-H coupling of dipolar 2-*H*-benzothiazoles end-capped with triphenylamine moieties affords highly fluorescent 2,2'-bibenzothiazoles with D-π-A-π-D architecture displaying large two-photon absorption (TPA) cross-sections (543–1252 GM) in the near-infrared region. The notably higher TPA performance as compared to quadrupolar π-systems with a widely-used 2,2'-bipyridine core, along with the ease of the synthesis and chelating N[^]N ability makes the title biheteroaryl platform an attractive building block for a large scope of functional dyes exploiting nonlinear optical phenomena.

Nonlinear optical (NLO) media are among the smartest materials giving rise to modern laser technologies, including ultrafast all-optical signal processing,¹ high-capacity optical data storage² or 3D microfabrication.³ NLO active molecules are also vital in high-resolution bioimaging, exploiting a second-harmonic generation⁴ and/or two-photon-excited fluorescence (TPEF),⁵ and they serve as singlet oxygen photosensitisers in photodynamic therapy (PDT)^{6,7} by using near-IR light. The latter two techniques take advantage of the two-photon absorption (TPA) - the third-order NLO phenomenon referring to a simultaneous absorption of two photons of half the nominal excitation energy by a single molecule. This process enables the excitation of molecules by low-energy light in the biological transparency window (700–1000 nm), which is beneficial in an in-depth tissue / material penetration as compared to one-photon absorption (OPA) in the visible region, and allows more control and higher spatial resolution via quadratic dependence of the TPA rate on the incident laser light intensity.^{5,6}

Applications of conventional OPA dyes in TPEF microscopy or two-photon excited PDT suffer from small TPA cross-sections,

δ_{TPA} , often limited to a few tens of GM units. These require high laser powers and long exposure times, which may result in photochemical damage of an irradiated object. To fully benefit from the advantages of TPA, a quest for dyes possessing large δ_{TPA} together with high quantum yields, good photostability and cell permeability (keeping thus molecular size as small as possible), is still a hot topic in material science.^{5,6,8}

In this regard, employment of suitable heteroaromatic scaffolds in π-conjugated systems with intramolecular charge-transfer (ICT) is a useful design strategy in the construction of TPA active dyes allowing to meet specific application requirements and to achieve large δ_{TPA} within a confined chromophore space by proper arrangement of heteroatoms or entire heteroaromatic blocks within the π-system.⁵⁻⁹ Of particular popularity are low-cost and readily available *N*-heteroaromatics, such as pyridines (py), pyrazines (pz), 2,2'-bipyridines (bpy), or benzothiazoles (btz), owing to their electron-accepting properties, photochemical resistance and ease of their further functionalization through protonation, *N*-alkylation or *N*-coordination to metal fragments allowing to tune solubility and NLO properties of π-systems thereof.^{7,9-14}

In most benzothiazole-derived π -conjugated systems reported so far, electron-donating triarylamine moieties are attached to the heteroarene C-2 position due to its higher reactivity, which however limits their further facile functionalization at the less reactive benzene ring.¹² In addition, we have shown that placing triarylamine branches to the C-6 position of the btz unit is more favourable in terms of larger TPA activity, especially when the auxiliary electron-withdrawing group (EWG) is attached to the C-2 carbon.⁸ While dipolar C-6 substituted 2-H-benzothiazoles without additional EWG substituent display small TPA action cross-sections comparable with other commonly-used OPA fluorophores,⁸ our latest DFT computational studies revealed that the TPA activity of these derivatives should be largely enhanced (> 20 -fold) by their transformation to hitherto elusive quadrupolar 2,2'-bibenzenothiazoles (Scheme 1). The latter derivatives are also expected to show high emission quantum yields due to the structural similarity of their π -core with the skeleton of firefly luciferin and they could benefit from feasible bidentate N^N coordination, resembling the chemistry of bipyridine-cored π -systems widely used in NLO applications,^{7,11-13} but with higher TPA efficiency.

Scheme 1. DFT (CAM-B3LYP/6-311++G)¹⁵ computed TPA cross-sections, δ_{TPA} , in their low-energy resonant maxima ($S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ for D- π -A, $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ for D- π -A- π -D) for pertinent triphenylamine-functionalized 2-H-benzothiazole (left), 2,2'-bibenzenothiazole (middle) and 2,2'-bipyridine (right) together with their advantageous/disadvantageous features (see SI for Computational details and analysis).**

Although unsubstituted 2,2'-bibenzenothiazole (bisbtz) has recently attracted the attention of material chemists as a bidentate N^N ligand in the construction of efficient red- or NIR-light emitters for OLED devices,¹⁶ its triarylamine-functionalized derivatives have remained so far synthetically unavailable and their properties unexplored.

To prove the anticipated TPA performance of this quadrupolar heteroaromatic platform, we firstly developed a facile access to a variety of dipolar (D- π -A) 2-H-benzothiazoles (**btz-I-VI**) bearing arylamine moieties attached to the C-6 position of the heteroaromatic scaffold via π -spacers of different length. A key intermediate – 6-iodobenzothiazole (**1**) was prepared by a quantitative hydrodechlorination of 6-iodo-2-chlorobenzothiazole (**2**) with KI and H₃PO₂. **2** was obtained by direct iodination of commercially available 2-chlorobenzothiazole with I₂/KMnO₄ or in higher yield using a two-step sequence – selective C-6 iodination of benzothiazol-2(3H)-one and subsequent chlorination with POCl₃ (Scheme 2).^{10c} Triarylamine moieties with or without π -spacer were introduced to the benzothiazole scaffold via Pd-catalyzed cross-coupling reactions of **1** with corresponding arylacetylenes, arylboronic

acids or *in situ* generated arylvinylboronic acids under Sonogashira and Suzuki-type conditions, respectively (Scheme 2). The derivative with the shortest π -conjugation **btz-I** was obtained in a reasonable yield by direct arylation of readily available benzothiazole-6-amine (**3**) with a highly reactive triphenylsulfonium triflate (Ph₃SOTf).¹⁷ Attempts to introduce NPh₂ group to **1** by means of Buchwald-Hartwig amination¹⁸ with diphenylamine were unsuccessful, while the coupling of **3** with bromobenzene afforded a mixture of *N*-monoarylated amine and *N*,2-diphenylbenzothiazole-6-amine (see SI). To avoid the undesired C-2 arylation, we also explored a route starting by aromatic nucleophilic substitution of **3** with 2.2 eq. of 4-fluoronitrobenzene, followed by reduction with H₂/Pd and hydrodeamination of the two pendant amino groups in **4** by *t*BuONO/THF and an aqueous solution of H₃PO₂, which afforded **btz-I** from **3** in the overall yield only slightly higher than that of the direct arylation.

The *push-pull* 2-H-benzothiazoles (**btz-I-VI**) were subsequently transformed to desired 2,2'-bibenzenothiazoles in one-step oxidation reaction by inexpensive and commonly-used Cu(OAc)₂,¹⁹ affording the products in 62-96% yields (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Synthesis of dipolar (D- π -A) arylamine-functionalized 2-H-benzothiazoles and their transformation to quadrupolar 2,2'-bibenzenothiazoles by Cu^{II}-mediated oxidative homocoupling. Visual demonstration of the changes in absorption and emission (under 365 nm UV light) of btz and bisbtz derivatives

This synthetic approach takes advantage of oxidative C–H homocoupling, which is a convenient and atom-economical method for the construction of bi(hetero)aryl skeletons.²⁰ While the homocoupling of donor-substituted 2-H-benzothiazoles in xylene proceeds also with the substoichiometric amount of Cu(OAc)₂, the reaction requires a much longer reaction time until complete conversion (ca. 36 h when using 0.2 eq. of oxidant). The reaction can be accelerated by using nitrobenzene as the solvent, but due to its toxicity and very high boiling point we find xylene as a more convenient medium (see SI).

Structures of all **bisbtz** were confirmed spectroscopically and by elemental analysis, while representative **bisbtz-I** was also characterized by single crystal X-ray diffraction (Figure 1), showing a co-planar arrangement of two benzothiazole rings in the core. The C–C distance between two btz moieties is 1.456(2) Å, hinting at the efficient π -conjugation throughout the entire backbone with a partial C_{btz}=C_{btz} double-bond character. In line with DFT calculations, two heteroarene moieties adopt energetically favourable *s-trans* configuration, while *s-cis* conformers are computed to be thermodynamically less stable by ca. 24 kJ/mol.

Figure 1. Molecular structure of **bisbtz-I**. Solvent molecules are omitted for clarity and the displacement ellipsoids are drawn at 50% probability level (see SI for more details).

Target **bisbtz** dyes were subjected to measurements of UV-vis absorption and emission spectra (Figures 2a,b), as well as to TPA cross-sections, δ_{TPA} , via a TPEF method with femtosecond laser excitation at wavelengths of 730–870 nm (Figure 3). The squared dependence of up-converted fluorescence intensity on input laser power, confirming a two-photon excitation mechanism, is shown in Figure S10 in SI. One-photon and two-photon spectral characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Photophysical Properties of 2,2'-Bibenzothiazoles bisbtz-I–VI in Comparison with Pertinent Dipolar 2-H-Benzothiazoles and bpy Congener of bisbtz-VI in Toluene

dye	λ_{abs} [nm]	ϵ_{abs} [M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹]	λ_f [nm]	Φ_f	$\langle\tau\rangle$ [ns]	λ_{TPA} [nm]	δ_{TPA} [GM]	Φ_f	δ_{TPA} [GM]
bisbtz-I	439	42 500	495	0.99	1.70	800	538	543	
bisbtz-II	419	43 700	496	0.82	1.34	800	480	585	
bisbtz-III	437	55 600	527	0.75	2.00	820	819	1092	
bisbtz-IV	428	65 100	497	0.86	1.22	810	873	1015	
bisbtz-V	441	49 000	527	0.68	1.92	840	679	998	
bisbtz-VI	450	74 300	518	0.75	1.24	830	939	1252	
btz-IV	365	31 500	405	0.75		730	34	46	
btz-VI	381	34 500	429	0.96		760	62	64	
bpy	392	52 100	443	0.64		780	135	210	

Figure 2. (a) UV-vis absorption ($c = 1 \times 10^{-5}$ M) and (b,c) emission ($c = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ M) of **bisbtz** dyes in toluene. (d) Frontier MOs of **bisbtz-I** relevant to intensive, lowest-energy OPA ($S_0 \rightarrow S_1$; HOMO \rightarrow LUMO) and TPA ($S_0 \rightarrow S_2$; HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO) transitions. (e) Nanosecond fluorescence dynamics for the **bisbtz** dyes in toluene solution ($c = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ M). The excitation wavelength was 400 nm and the detection was at the wavelength of emission maxima.

Figure 3. (a) TPA action cross-sections, $\delta_{TPA}\Phi_f$, and (b) TPA cross-sections, δ_{TPA} , of **bisbtz** dyes in toluene ($c = 2 \times 10^{-5}$ M). (c) Comparison of TPA action cross-sections and (d) TPA cross-sections of **bisbtz-IV** and **bisbtz-VI** with their dipolar congeners (**btz-IV**, **btz-VI**) and a bipyridine-cored quadrupole **bpy**. TPEF referenced to Rhodamine 6G ($c = 2 \times 10^{-5}$ M) in methanol as the standard (see SI for more details).

The absorption spectra of **bisbtz** dyes in toluene (Figure 2a) feature an intense band in the visible region with maxima λ_{abs} positioned at 419–450 nm. According to time-dependent DFT calculations, the low-energy transitions are associated with an intramolecular charge-transfer (ICT) from electron-rich arylamines to the bisbtz core (see HOMO and LUMO orbitals in Figure 2d). Note that some **bisbtz** derivatives display a

distinct shoulder peak on the low-energy side and this two-component pattern is also seen in emission spectra, which can be related to the vibronic coupling. The fluorescence in toluene (Figures 2b,c) is observed in the green spectral region with the most intense peaks at 495–527 nm, reaching very high emission quantum yields Φ_f of 0.68–0.99. The fluorescence dynamics exhibits a bi-exponential decay with a fast component with lifetime of 0.36–0.65 ns and a slower one of 1.42–2.46 ns (Figure 2e, Table S1 in SI). The slower component is considered as the main population decay mechanism while the faster one could be attributed to non-radiative decay due to conformational relaxation phenomena. The averaged lifetimes $\langle\tau\rangle$ of derivatives bearing pendant methoxy groups (**bisbtz-III**, **bisbtz-V**) are longer than those of the other dyes, pointing to a stronger stabilization of their excited state due to +M effect of OMe functionalities (Table 1).

Importantly, all **bisbtz** fluorophores exhibit high TPA cross-sections $\delta_{\text{TPA}} = 543\text{--}1252$ GM, exceeding those of many one-photon fluorophores²¹ and parent dipolar 2-H-benzothiazoles **btz** by more than an order of magnitude (Figure 3d), confirming thus the efficiency of the synthetic strategy (homocoupling of arylamine-functionalized C-H heteroarenes) in large TPA enhancement. TPEF maxima positions λ_{TPA} (800–840 nm) are less than twice that of the single-photon absorption λ_{abs} ($S_0 \rightarrow S_1$), implying a deeper $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition associated mainly with the HOMO–1 \rightarrow LUMO excitation. Both these MOs have the same *a* symmetry, obeying thus a parity selection rule for quadrupolar dyes (see also Figure S9 and Table S9 in SI).

TPA cross-sections of resonant maxima increase within the **bisbtz** series non-monotonically along with the elongation of the π -conjugation length, while vinylene π -spacer is found more efficient than the ethynylene linkage. Interestingly, introduction of peripheral methoxy groups to **bisbtz-II** led to about 2-fold TPA enhancement, while the same modification in the longer π -system (**bisbtz-IV** \rightarrow **bisbtz-V**) affected TPA activity marginally.

It is noteworthy that the TPA maximum cross-section of **bisbtz-VI** is ca. 6 times larger than that of bipyridine-cored congener **bpy**^{12,13} measured in toluene under identical TPEF conditions (literature data for **bpy** are 219 GM at 690 nm and 425 GM at 780 nm in chloroform and DMF, respectively).^{12,13} Although the TPA performance of **bisbtz-VI** in chloroform is somewhat lowered ($\delta_{\text{TPA}} = 1018$ GM at 840 nm), it is still about 4.6 times higher than that of **bpy**, yet with emission maximum shifted to the orange spectral region (Figures S4 and S12 in SI). The TPA superiority of **bisbtz** scaffold can be ascribed according to the three-state model²² to notably larger transition-dipole moment between the ground and the first excited state ($\mu_{01} = 17.8$ D), which is also reflected in higher molar extinction coefficient (cf. ϵ_{abs} for **bisbtz-VI** and **bpy** in Table 1), larger first-excited-to-second-excited state transition moment ($\mu_{12} = 13.4$ D) and smaller detuning energy ($E_1 - E_2/2 = 1.32$ eV) as compared to **bpy**-cored congener with $\mu_{01} = 14.4$ D, $\mu_{12} = 9.9$ D and $E_1 - E_2/2 = 1.65$ eV. This, in turn, allows to achieve higher TPA activity within the confined chromophore space with a shorter π -bridge, that is beneficial in the engineering of small-molecular probes for TPEF microscopy or photosensitizers for PDT.

In addition, our pilot studies on complexation of **bisbtz-I** with transition-metal carbonyl compounds, such as $\text{ReCl}(\text{CO})_5$, confirmed its bidentate N \wedge N coordination, while forming a purple-coloured complex $[\text{ReCl}(\text{CO})_3(\text{bisbtz-I})]$ with low-energy ICT absorption bands positioned at 536 and 562 nm

(Figure S5 in SI). Complexation via central azole N \wedge N nitrogen atoms is unambiguously manifested by a high-frequency ¹⁵N NMR azole shift from –70 ppm in the free ligand (**bisbtz-I**) to –123 ppm in the Re^{I} complex, which is in the excellent agreement with ¹⁵N NMR shifts computed for the considered species by means of relativistic calculations (Table S11 in SI).²³ To conclude, homocoupling of *push-pull* C-H heteroarenes is demonstrated to be a simple and atom-economical strategy to achieve large (~20-fold) TPA enhancement. Outstanding one-photon and two-photon absorption properties in the visible and near-IR region, respectively, along with the chelating N \wedge N ability, make triarylamine-functionalized 2,2'-bibenzothiazoles a more attractive alternative to notorious donor-functionalized *bpy* π -systems. Based on the high TPA cross-sections, strong emission and bidentate coordination, the title quadrupolar biheteroarenes provide a privileged platform paving the way to a large scope of efficient, small- to medium-sized, NLO-phores with diverse (dipolar, quadrupolar, octupolar) architectures, properties of which can be easily tailored by modifying the peripheral arylamine moieties and/or metal fragments.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Experimental and computational details, synthetic procedures, compounds characterization, crystal structure data for **bisbtz-I**, computed TPA cross-sections (PDF)

FAIR Data is available as Supporting Information for Publication and includes the primary NMR FID files for all new compounds. See [FID for Publication](#) for additional information.

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website.

Accession Codes

CCDC 2056840 (**bisbtz-I**) contain the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif, or by emailing data_request@ccdc.cam.ac.uk, or by contacting The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; fax: +44 1223 336033.

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